

ClairCity: Citizen-led air pollution reduction in cities

D4.15 Mutual Learning Workshop Complete – Last city (April 2018)

1 Document Details

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Description	<p>This deliverable is the follow up of D4.14 Mutual Learning Workshop Complete – First City (Bristol MLW report) delivered in August 2017. D4.15 Mutual Learning Workshop Complete – Last city summarises the Mutual Learning Workshops (MLW) held in the other pilot cities (Amsterdam, Sosnowiec and Ljubljana) and regions (Liguria and Aveiro). The MLW brought together expert stakeholders to share and discuss transport- and heating policies, and derived health risk factors in a changing city environment, now and in the future (2020-2030-2050). This report contains the general concept of the MLW, the summary of the Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria MLW, the scenario outputs and conclusions. The differences in reporting are due to the fact that each city / region tailored the workshop to the local needs and context. All participants of the MLW signed consent forms allowing us to mention their names and use the pictures taken at the workshops for our deliverables. The extended reports for each city will be uploaded onto the ClairCity website.</p>

2 Version History

Version	Updated By	Date	Changes / Comments
V1	Various authors (see 'Contributions and Acknowledgements')	1/11/17 - 16/4/18	Version 1 based on city and region reports of the MLW results
V2	Eva Csobod, Peter Szuppinger	16/4/18	Update the structure of the report
V3	Various authors (see 'Contributions and Acknowledgements')	17/4/18	Update of the conclusions

V4	Eva Csobod, Final version of the report	23/4/18	Update according to the review
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3 Contributions and Acknowledgements

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4 Executive Summary

The activity belongs to the work package Citizens and Stakeholder Engagement, WP4.4 – Citizens and their Health, Task 4.4.1 Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop. The aim is to empower citizens to better understand the specific challenges and opportunities that their city currently offers and engage them into moving towards reduce pollutants emissions and carbon footprints, improved air quality and decreased health risks. This is achieved as part of overall perceptions and ideas of citizens on sustainable lifestyles and a *'better quality of life'* within their city in the future. The main outcomes will support the policy development of the cities towards 2050 in the field of integrated city planning, air quality and climate change.

The REC (WP4 lead) design of the Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshops (MLW); the content, methodology, structure, the potential stakeholders and timeframe. The MLW is implemented by the partners and cities/regions. The first city was Bristol. UWE and the Bristol city adapted the proposed method in MLW Guidelines (see in the Annex of the D4.14) to the local needs and conditions. After Bristol, Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria region completed the MLW workshop with success. The outcomes of the MLW contribute to the Stakeholder workshops in the cities/regions in autumn 2018 and the WP6 on Policy and WP7 on Scenario building. In total 117 participants were involved in the MLWs.

5 Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop

5.1.1 MLW Concept

The MLW is designed for different stakeholders who are engaged in environment, health issues and policies in Bristol (reported in D 4.14), Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria region and ready to participate in the MLW. The participants of the workshops were stakeholders, selected NGOs, social city groups, health and environmental organisations, universities, relevant department of the pilot cities, who are involved in the air quality, public health and carbon management issues, planning and activities in the city (local level), or regional and national level.

5.1.2 Workshop Aim

To develop routes to a “clean air”, healthy cities/regions by 2050 by understanding specific challenges and opportunities for organisations, and engaging them to identify actions, milestones and priorities towards 2050.

5.1.3 Facilitators

- Eva Csobod, WP4.4.1 task coordinator (REC)
- Gabor Heves, Peter Szuppinger, task facilitators (REC)
- Amsterdam: Irati Artola (Trinomics)
- Aveiro region: Vera Rodrigues (University of Aveiro)
- Liguria region: Rita Vaccaro (Techne)
- Ljubljana: Sabina Popit (Municipality of Ljubljana), Nadja Zeleznik (REC)
- Sosnowiec: Edyta Wykurz (Municipality of Sosnowiec)

5.1.4 Participants

Participants of the workshops were from a range of organisations: City Council, NGOs and campaign groups, health and environmental organisations, partnerships and consultancies, businesses, universities, and transport providers. The detailed participant lists are in the individual city/region report on the project website.

5.1.5 Organisations

Participants were invited through a number of routes (invites included a link to register for the workshop on Eventbrite), coordinated by the city/region contacts by invitation letter via email and direct calls. Social media was used for information delivery about the events

5.1.6 Logistics

Two rooms were used for the workshop: one set up for a discussion with two/three keynote speakers and one set up for the poster creation and group work.

Tea, coffee and croissants were available on arrival. More tea and coffee plus cookies were provided at the break.

5.1.7 Resources

Participant sign-up sheet

Consent forms

Participant information sheets

Large posters for Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria region 2020, 2030, and challenges and barriers of the cities/regions towards 2050

Ppt slide presentation

Pens, scissors, stickers, sellotape, blue tack, post it notes, paper (for poster creation)

6 Agenda

9:00: Arrival and sign in (with tea, coffee and croissants)

Start

9:30: Welcome and outline of programme

9:40: Panel session with keynote speakers (environment and health sector)

10:15: Panel session Q&A

10:30: Strategies and creating visions: 2020, 2030 & 2050

11:10: Break

(With Tea and Coffee)

11.25: Challenges and barriers – 2020-2030-2050

11:45: Scenario sessions (in 3-5 groups)

Milestones, priorities and actions

12.30: Scenario knowledge sharing discussion

Milestones, priorities and actions

12.50: Conclusions/closing words

13.0 End

More details about the agenda and speakers are in the individual city/region report on the project website.

7 Reports of the Mutual Learning Workshops: cities and regions

7.1 Amsterdam

7.1.1 Welcome and introduction

A short presentation about ClairCity i.e. objective, partners, WPs and particularly WP4 (Engagement of citizens and stakeholders) was given to explain *why* we are having this Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW).

After that there were three presentations from three speakers from the Municipality of Amsterdam. The aim of these presentations was not to enter in discussion but to provide background and context for the interactive activity working in groups that followed (see tables in the individual report).

7.1.2 Speaker 1: Air Quality and Health

The presentation, which was titled “Air Quality: in the past, in the present and in the future”, dealt with What is air pollution? Where does it come from (i.e. Sources) and the effects on health at all ages Some of the highlights presented:

- Through an image of a the NO₂ concentrations in Europe as measured by satellite based on a colour code it was shown how densely populated areas – including Amsterdam, have high air pollution concentration.

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- Health effects of air pollution at all ages (throughout a lifetime) were named
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- In fact, environmental pollution (where the majority can be accrued to air pollution) is after smoking the most important factor affecting disease or death.
- London Smog in 1952 – 4000 deaths in a couple of days. This had to do with coal. - The response of the Netherlands was legislation. The Netherlands also heated homes with coal at that time but a coal ban was implemented; the Netherlands has gas since the 60s.
- In 1993 a revolutionary article came out in “The New England Journal of Medicine” explaining that it is not only episodes of smog that can be detrimental to health, but that living in a polluted place permanently (and the constant exposure to pollution concentrations to levels that are at first glance not so worrisome) could be at least as damaging.
- It is known that “there is no such things as air pollution level without an effect in health”. It is hard as the Municipality of Amsterdam to decide how to go about it and deal with hotspots or air pollution vs good air quality as a whole in the city.
- In the future by 2050 there will be more electric cars (zero emission cars) and more space for public transport, bikes, pedestrians (than for cars). Cars as we know them today will be extinct.
- An important remark was made on the public misunderstanding of air pollution vs CO2 emissions through illustrating an article in the newspaper talking about ‘dirty cars’ whereas the article had to do with CO2 emissions and energy efficiency and not with the emissions of pollutants (‘Clean’ is often related with low- or CO2 – less whereas the term may be more adequate to address air pollution).

7.1.3 Speaker 2: Amsterdam and transport vision 2050

The presentation talked about trends in transport and expected people commuting. Some pictures were shown of Amsterdam in 1984. Cars were dominant in the streets, there were no trees nor bikes. While in 1984 people were leaving the city (to go somewhere else), since some decades and currently Amsterdam is growing and growing.

Transport dependent on spatial developments, economic developments, social demographic developments. More people also means more traffic. In fact globalisation means more traffic of all kinds (e.g. we fly everywhere). For decades, the car has been preferred for getting out of the city, but the bike is preferred in the city. Logistics will possibly also change and influence transport – ‘just in time’ approaches and 3D printing technologies will call for more local production.

Transport will evolve to be cleaner, faster, more comfortable and save. Cars in movement take up most of the public space and then cars parked. More efficient use of space is the ultimate challenge for crowded cities such as Amsterdam: from car ownership to car-sharing. In the next 10 years, the expected trends are:

- Urbanisation continues, also of the periphery
- Partial shift to electric or hydro (pace of this in the Netherlands will depend on EU legislation)
- Further automatization (effects in the city unknown)
- More influence of big data in our daily lives
- The power of big companies larger than that of the states

The Municipal government is planning to intervene by: setting environmental zones (also for private cars), giving priority to pedestrians and bikes, and shifting parking from streets to parking sites.

Some key questions for the Municipality are: “are we going to travel more and further if travel times become shorter?”; “how vulnerable is our current system in terms of, how dependent are we on technology (backward movement e.g. back to basics) and of scarce resources (e.g. clean water)?”

The conclusion is that the future is difficult to predict. “Transport is becoming cleaner but the pace at which it will do so is unknown”.

7.1.4 Speaker 3: Amsterdam and energy vision 2050

‘Sustainability’ in terms of energy for the Municipality of Amsterdam has to do with CO2 emission reduction.

For electricity the transition is towards locally-produced energy. They would like to have more windmills but the Province of North-Holland thinks differently.

As for as heating, in Amsterdam 90% of homes and business are heating through gas. This is undesirable from a CO2 point of view. Moreover, the long-term vision for Amsterdam is to be gas-free by 2050. The main alternative is district heating. For this there have been discussions with housing corporations and other stakeholders. However this is not very popular among people -- district heating does not have a good image (when you Google it, it seems that you only get problems related to it e.g. lack of transparency in price). The municipality is aware that you can’t make this shift overnight. This needs to happen from a neighbourhood to neighbourhood basis. Affordability is a big issue. Natural gas is a very developed (convenient, openness and possibility to choose suppliers) and cheap source of energy, so it is not

straightforward to make the shift to district heating. Citizens also get concerned about the price of the alternative. Therefore, citizen consent needed, as measures are highly invasive

A remark made on wood pellets for heating was that the Municipality is certainly not going to stimulate that due to the effects on air pollution (they took this out deliberately of the eligible measures for 'energy loans' that the Municipality was offering for sustainable heating) but there is currently no intention of banning that.

7.1.5 Plenary Discussion

- The sustainability of district heating was questioned.
- To heat homes in a 100% electric way, requires very thick/good insulation of the homes or buildings in question. This is unlikely to be possible in some of the neighbourhoods of Amsterdam.
- There is currently little on 'infrastructure' for energy in the 'Sustainability Agenda'. Whether such a chapter is going to be included in the Agenda was enquired. The answer was that there will certainly be something put into writing on infrastructure but whether that will be in the Sustainability Agenda or on a separate Infrastructure Agenda still -or somewhere else- still needs to be decided.

7.1.6 Introduction to the working groups sessions

This was the most interactive, hands-on part of the workshop. Participants were divided in three tables to work on two sessions:

Work session 1: where are we going towards, and how fast are we going, what are the actions?

Work session 2: what are the barriers and solutions that we currently see and expect we encounter?

Below we summarise the discussions that took place on each of the tables:

7.1.7 Work session 1 – Actions and Scenarios by 2020, 2030 and 2050

Table 1:

Until now more and more people move into the city, which might negatively impact the air quality. On the other hand, migration happens in wave-like patters. New forms of high-speed mobility might enable people to live further away from the city, but work in the city. If the increase in population and visitors in Amsterdam is sustained, this will push the cars out of the city because of competition for space. On the short term the first neighbourhoods will be uncoupled from the gas grid, for newly built neighbourhoods this will become common practice.

On the mid-term cooperative models for renovating the existing built environment will become common practice, and as a result the demand for gas will decline faster than the supply available from domestic gas production. By 2030 the situation will be a bit chaotic as the energy system and the economy in general are not yet in equilibrium, but still changing at a rapid pace. This change will be welcomed by some people, while it might generate anxiety for others. In 2050, the largest part of the energy transition will be done, and passenger transport and the energy consumption in households will be 100% electric.

Table 2:

The actions and scenarios mainly focussed on energy, rather than air quality. The table started off with placing a dot on the horizon. It was agreed that in 2050 all energy for the city was produced in a sustainable way (i.e. wind, solar, biomass, geothermal, etc).

There was a discussion whether houses would be self-sufficient or that a collective energy-system would be the way to go. Two people in the group believed in the concept of houses being self-sufficient. The person from the energy department of the city of Amsterdam did not agree. He argued that there is not enough space in the city (e.g. roofs for solar panels) to produce the demand for energy. There will be need for a collective system, such as district heating. After a discussion it was agreed that the city will need a collective system but that there also should be room for individuals to be self-sustaining.

The RIVM argued that agriculture is a big problem. It adds a lot to the background concentrations. Cities should educate people and try to stimulate people to consume less meat. In general education and raising awareness was recognised as an important topic.

The person from the energy department of the city of Amsterdam wondered whether money should be spent on education/raising awareness or on actual measures. He is inclined to spend money on measures rather than on behaviour. He argued that a lot of people do not care how their house is heated, they just want a warm house and warm water coming from the tap.

As actions by 2030 it was agreed that there should be legislation that all new and renovated houses should have solar panels. By 2050 all houses in the Netherlands should have solar panels.

Table 3:

The table participants focused primarily on transport. Car transport in the city was discouraged up to 2025 by a segmentation of the city like in Groningen and in Bologna, in combination with more shared cars and improved public transport from the periphery into the city. The bikers interest group representative envisioned fast and slow bike transport lanes, with fast routes East-West, North – South. The existing ‘blue number plate’ allowing certain low-speed scooters to go on bikepaths should be abolished. This should go in combination with a ‘healthy urban route planner’ – an app for bikes to be able to select the cleanest routes (such apps exist in Oslo, the US). For the transport of goods innovative developments – such as shared transport opportunities for food would be needed.

In the longer term, the city should be car free, apart from vehicles delivering goods.
Obligatory PV on all roofs.

Table 4:

The group started the discussion with what we would like to achieve by 2050:

Short wrap up of 2050 goals:

- Amsterdam home heating fossil fuel free
- Homes energy neutral or energy positive
- Road traffic CO₂ neutral, emission free
- No car (ownership) within city
- Citizens of Amsterdam should be more aware of the exact sources of the energy they use.
- Air pollution is considered to pose no problem by 2050, since most road traffic will be emission free by then.

As for as the goals by 2020 and 2030 which were considered intermediate:

By 2030, the Amsterdam LEZ (Low Emission Zone) for cars will be tightened as to which cars will be admitted in an area. This will cause the air quality to be healthy (preferably by WHO standards) by 2030.

By 2020 all newly built homes will have no connection to natural gas, and by 2030 all new homes and office buildings will be energy positive.

7.1.8 “Mood in the room” exercise

Between the two work sessions, we introduced an “activating” short activity to find out about the mood in the room. Statements were presented and participants were asked to choose a side (right, if they agreed with the statement; left, if they disagreed with the statement).

The opinions were divided for the following statements:

“The citizens won’t accept fast changes in terms of sustainability measures (to improve air quality and CO₂ emissions)”;

“By 2030 there will be no more cars in the city centre of Amsterdam”; and

“Sustainable electricity will solve our transport and heating problems”, although for this latter the majority through it WILL.

The statement with a clear majority was:

“The new Climate Plan of the Government will be revolutionary for CO₂ reduction in cities”, where the majority of participants thought it WON’T.

7.1.9 Work session 2 – Barriers and solutions by 2050

Table 1:

In the transition to the scenario described in the first session, there will be several barriers to be overcome, including:

- The issue that society is no longer used to large publicly funded infrastructure projects, as the electricity grid, gas grid and sewage system have been in place for a long time already. However, the strong electrification needed for the transition to renewable energy sources, will also require large public investments in electricity infrastructure, especially at the local (neighbourhood) level.
- There is a lack of expertise among professionals to provide, produce and install new types of technologies and buildings that are needed to transform society sustainably.
- In the construction sector the financial crisis stimulated sustainable initiatives as this enabled project developers to stand out from the crowd in a difficult market. Currently, the demand for new construction projects is so large that companies no longer have to do their best to provide sustainable solutions in order to undermine competition.
- There is often a mismatch between the people who make the investments in 'clean' technologies as opposed to those who benefit from it.
- Because of lobbying by established regime actors (large companies) there is still no level playing field between fossil energy technologies and sustainable alternatives.

However, the barriers mentioned above are not unsurmountable, solutions to overcome the barriers include:

- We need to make our education system more future-proof, we need visionary education. On the side of professional education, it is important that the state of the art sustainable technologies and concepts are taught and not the old polluting ones. Also, a more visionary type of education provides an opportunity for the development of innovative and creative ideas which results in business opportunities.
- We need to create a level playing field by taxing polluting modes of transport and energy applications and stimulating sustainable solutions.
- On the mid-term some strict regulations might be needed to discourage polluting/unsustainable behaviours.
- Because of the reduction in demand for gasoline it will become hard to find a gas station.

Table 2:

The group identified several barriers. Again the discussion focussed mainly on energy.

Existing interests and differences in governance (local, provincial and national) were identified as barriers. For instance cities might be more progressive than regional or national government. And citizens might be more progressive than a city. For instance Amsterdam would like to have windmills in the harbour, but the province (who has to give the permit does not agree. A small scale project in Amsterdam (the Ceuvel) wanted to be self-sustaining but found the city of Amsterdam in their way. They just started doing it and the city became interested and let them continue.

It was discussed that there should be (more) room for bottom up initiatives. Room to experiment and learn on the way. Small scale projects can become mainstream if successful.

Table 3:

Some of the barriers named were the mindset citizens, the use of space by different means of transport in a limited space, safety issues related to electrical bikes in bicycle lanes which can ride faster than regular bikes, investment possibilities for citizens, the costs of new heating infrastructure, resistance of car and scooter companies and stakeholders

Solutions are awareness raising (the example of the joint development -between energy providers, a bank and the Municipality- of a so-called 'Energy Hub' to speed up the energy transition in the South-East of Amsterdam was mentioned); benchmarking and naming/shaming – neighbourhoods, car stakeholders (see below the picture that depicts the statement that the participant from the bikers association made in her street by filling up her car with a tree); Co-creation processes with citizens; Offering lower costs – subsidies for energy efficiency and insulation measures; Showing the benefits of more space in the city – green in the city

Table 4:

We did not discuss barriers and solutions to a great extent, but one of the most important barriers that was discussed was the way how to seduce/coerce citizens in a certain direction. In general people tend to prefer the use of highly individualised types of transportation (ie. cars over public transport). Of course the people who own a car and want to park their car within the city pay for it already, but the price they pay is not high enough. The discussion focused for a large deal on how to make people pay for the space they use and the CO₂ they emit. The ideas on how to make people aware of this problem differed quite a lot. Some people at the table believed that creating more awareness and taking away legal barriers for new experiments (ie. on car sharing or 'mobility as a service') would create a bottom up effect that will spread automatically. Others were more pessimistic about this and suggestions were made that CO₂ emissions as well as the use of space should be taxed.

7.1.10 Discussion and conclusions (plenary)

In a plenary session, one participant in each table was asked to report to the rest of the room the summary of the work on their table.

Table 1: Summary

By 2020:

- Cars need to get out of the city
- First districts get rid off gas (small scale)
- New built buildings are gas-free

By 2030:

- Collective renovations of housing will take place
- From 2020 until 2030 no more high temperature district heating (low temperature district heating)
- Gas becomes far less popular

By 2050:

- Transport is 100% electric
- All energy consumption in a neighbourhood will be powered by electricity

Barriers:

- There will be 'losers' in the transitions
- There will be chaos: energy is produced locally, it will be hard to keep an overview
- Public investment in sustainable infrastructure is challenging
- Mismatch between the costs and benefits of sustainable energy

Solutions:

- Legislation: ban fossil fuels

Table 2: Summary

By 2020:

- Built environment more sustainable: lots of deep renovation and new built buildings sustainable (mandatory solar panels)

By 2030:

- Only non-polluting, emission-free cars in the city

Barriers:

- Price from gas/oil is low
- Lack of shared vision between different levels of government

Solutions:

- Legislation for the built environment
- Education: investing in behavior

Table 3: Summary

By 2020:

- Awareness raising of neighbours, measuring with neighbours
- Getting rid of light scooters

- Developing 'healthy route' information for citizens to decide the way they choose to walk, bike

By 2030:

- Electric, shared car systems in Amsterdam only
- Safety for bikes (max. tot 25 km/hour electric mopeds in the bike path)
- More greenery, more public gardens and parks

By 2050:

- Between 2030 and 2050 the city fully car-free (some goods transport can still circulate)
- A comprehensive public transport network (running every 3 minutes)
- Shared good transportations
- Mandatory solar panels for every roof

Barriers:

- Neighbours: citizens can't take their own decisions if they belong to a home owners associations
- The mindset of people for instance a negative image of district heating
- Innovative transport will perhaps undermine the safety of cyclists
- More transport types also mean more competition for public space

Solutions:

- Very good bike infrastructure (even better e.g. broader)
- Very good and well-connected network of public transport

Table 4: Summary

By 2020:

- Only new-built buildings do not have natural gas
- More mobility options come into place

By 2030:

- All new built buildings are energy positive

By 2050:

- Emission-free transport
- Local production of energy by individuals
- More public transport, more bikes

Barriers:

- The main barrier that was discussed was on how to make citizens aware and willing to take action themselves, regarding climate change.

Solutions:

- 'Environmental zones' increasingly stringent. New 'environmental zones' have to come into place for all types of transport eventually (towards an emission free transport by 2050)
- CO2 needs to be priced! This serves many of the current challenges. It also helps people make fair choices.

7.1.11 Final discussion

Some further remarks were that:

- Nothing mentioned about busses (whereas these are high up on the list in other Dutch cities). This may be because there are already measures planned to make public transport in Amsterdam -including busses- emission free by 2025.
- The fact that citizens are aware of the problem does not mean they will act upon that (70% of the people know that climate change is happening but very few do something about it). For some it may be simply not be a priority or are not interested.
- "There is no such thing as 'the car driver', 'the cyclist', etc – we all have many roles and needs we work, we are parents, we cycle, we drive.
- Stakeholders (industry, government, citizens) need to work together; we have to do this together because it is complex.
- Pricing pollution is something that needs to be discussed. Transport for instance needs to become more expensive. That will have large consequences for behavior of citizens as stuff as well will become more expensive. However, dilemmas remain – for instance petrol versus diesel, one better for climate, the other better for air quality – how do you price that.

7.1.12 Main conclusions

Visions

- Participants share the vision that improvements are needed regarding more public transport, more room for biking and stimulation of electrical private transport;
- Some believe that the city can become completely car-free within the city-ring;
- Many believe that individual transport will remain important, even with improved public transport;
- The city council in the discussion rather promoted central systems (district heating), whereas others believed in the possibilities of all-individual zero-energy houses;
- Also, the city council preferred in the discussion concrete measures over awareness raising;
- Participants do not believe that current government action will be sufficient to achieve targets;

- Overall the vision for the city is that of a very green, clean, pleasant city with very good network of public transport and only electric private transport.

Barriers and solutions

- Large infrastructure (district heating) versus individual choice (individual zero energy housing): no solution provided
- Expertise from professionals in the built environment needed: skills of the construction sector
- No level playing field between sustainable and fossil technologies: taxing, financial incentives
- Mismatch between those who invest and those who profit: no solution provided
- Mismatch between interests on different governance levels (city want turbines, province doesn't allow): no solution provided

7.2 Ljubljana

7.2.1 Introduction

Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop (MLW) in Ljubljana took place on 15th of March 2018 on the premises of Ljubljana municipality City Hall. The workshop was held with different stakeholders to share and discuss the health risk factors in the city environment now and within the timescale of the future scenarios (2020-2030-2050). The workshop reflected multi-disciplinary context and discussed preventive measures of air quality, climate change and health issues. The mutual learning workshop provided opportunity for exchange of national/city systems and practices in health, environment and innovation (e.g. smart cities). It created further innovative tools for mutual learning to improve air quality, reduce carbon footprint and improve public health (with special attention given to children and senior citizens).

The MLW was performed according to the agenda, given in Annex 1 in the D.4.14., and included theoretical part, with several presentations given by representatives of competent institutions, the site tour with all attending the workshop and with round table to discuss the future strategies for improvement of air quality in Ljubljana center. At the MLW there were four speakers, two from the National Health Institute, as they had worked on a LIFE EU project MED HISS, and two representatives from National Urban Institute, that are now working on a national project VENAZDRAVJE (Out for health). They are all great experts at the field of health in urban environment.

The MLW was attended by 15 participants (Figure 1) as in the List of participants (Annex 2). The attendees were having background from geography, architecture, health, medicine, economy, land scape and urbanists, security, physics and chemistry. Invitation was sent to the representatives of non-governmental organization CIPRA, Faculty of Art (Department for Geography), Faculty of social science (Department for spatial sociology), Faculty of Architecture and urban planning, Institute for transfer and knowledge application at the Faculty of Health, IPOP – Institute for spatial policies, EUDAIMONIA – Institute for society of

quality life and Environmental center, that is connecting several NGOs in Ljubljana, working on Clair City connected topics.

7.2.2 Course of the workshop

The MLW started with welcome introduction given by Municipality Ljubljana representative Ms. Sabina Popit. She shortly presented the ClairCity project, the main objectives of the project, how it is performed and who are the participants. She then briefly presented the main issues to be addressed in the Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop and the agenda. She also provided information on the participants, describing the areas where they are coming from. All participants were invited to sign the statement that they agree that their view will be collected and used for development of the outcomes (Consent Form).

7.2.3 Plenary session

In this part two presentations were held as introduction and presentation of the overall context of air quality, climate change/management and health impacts on national and city level. In total four keynote speakers were selected and develop the relevant presentations with focus on the current health risk factors and the quality of the city environment.

The first presentation was given by Ms. Simona Perčič with co-author Ms. Simona Uršič from National Institute for public health (Figure 2) with the overview of EU LIFE project MED-HISS focusing on the impacts of air pollution on public health.

Figure 2: Outcomes from EU LIFE project MED-HISS, Ms. Simona Perčič

She presented the findings of WHO and other national organizations that air pollution is one of the major factors for health problems within population. According to the data only in 2012 3.7 mio of persons died due to the bad quality of air and pollution which is almost 7 % of all fatalities. Almost 90 % of city population are exposed to values above the limits of PM10, PM2,5, NOX , O3 and benzene in air. In addition, transport in cities is one of the major causes of air pollution, which statistically impact the health of newborns and is also cause of premature births. She talked about the impact of this particles to the health and presented results of several studies performed to evaluate effects of different pollutants.

Ms. Perčič then spoke about the results of the MED-HISS project, EU LIFE project covering several Mediterranean states, including Slovenia. The aim was to assess impact of long term exposure to pollutants of outdoor air on health, to support with evidences the changes of EU legislation and to develop new epidemiological surveillance measures with the data collected

from the environmental monitoring of air pollution, modelling and national health data (Figure 3). It was clear that the most vulnerable groups of citizens are patients with chronic diseases, children, elderly population and physically active people.

In the course of the project the common approach for the assessment of increased risk for health problems due to the air pollution was developed and is now available for future estimations. The most important aspects of the methodological approach used were spatial resolution of pollutant release estimates (4.4 km in horizontal resolution of the internal (nesting) calculation area with 185 × 167 calculating cells) and pooling of data at municipal level: geostatistical approach to kriging with external influence.

Ms Ina Šuklje Erjavec, UI RS (National Urban Institute) presented work on a national project VEN ZA ZDRAVJE (Out for health) which focus on health aspects and planning of green areas for healthier environment and public space in connection with physical activities of population. The project is supported by Ministry of health and will last until 2019.

Green surfaces affect the health and mood of people, we talk about the areas, which include green spaces, trees, forests, water resources, parks and similar. Ljubljana has already well organized spaces with green surfaces as can be seen from Figure 5. Green areas are ecosystems that implement ecosystem services: balancing, cultural role, supply, supporting functions. Green areas support a healthy lifestyle and activate their uses. The most common needs associated with green areas which are perceived by users are: contact with nature, breathing fresh air, the realization of creativity, the implementation of recreational and other activities. The project VEN ZA ZDRAVJE is addressing the justification and demonstration of measures to increase the use green areas: motivation and perception, accessibility and security, long-lasting mobility, participation in co-creation, types of activities, space characteristics for individual activities, space planning (holistic, systemic and integral). the problem of planning green areas is the implementation of plans, so awareness of decision makers is needed so that they can understand the whole process.

Mr. Luka Mladenovič (also UI RS) added the presentation on sustainable mobility with different concepts available in theory but also from the view of future possible developments. Sustainable mobility includes several possible transports: walking, cycling, public transport, special available services (Kavalir), use of Ljubljanica river.

7.2.4 Workshop session

The workshop was introduced by Ms Sabina Popit, MOL, who presented the main aims of the workshop: as Ljubljana city started to close the center for motor traffic already several years ago, now the city would like to increase the pedestrian cones also to other connected areas. Therefore, the workshop is organized to perform the guided tour and then to work within 2 groups to prepare the possible vision for this particular part until 2020, 2030 and 2050. In this respect the main related strategic documents adopted in Ljubljana municipality were briefly presented and discussed. The following were relevant:

- Until 2020: Environment protection program, Sustainable urban strategy and local energy concept;
- Until 2030: Ideal city – sustainable city – the Slovene capital, comprehensive traffic strategy

- Until 2050: Zero waste – the cultural changes

The participants first attended the guided tour (Figure 7) in the area of interest for the further work: it started at the City hall to the first bridge over Ljubljana (Šuštarški most), then continue on that side of the river to Krakovski nasip and turn back on the other side of Ljubljana to City hall. All participants discussed the current arrangements and possibilities for the improvements and enlargements of the pedestrian cone. This area is partly already free of traffic with exception of electric cars provided services for municipality (Kavalir). They combine the pedestrian cone with areas for bicycles, not very organized, a lot of spaces for restaurants and pubs and just refurbished banks of Ljubljana. On one side there are still street with cars. The Ljubljana river is navigable and a kind of river transport is already organised

After return to the meeting place, the participants were divided in 2 groups and asked to develop the strategy for area of interest until 2020, 2030 and 2050 with possible measures. The group were divided in a way to have participants with different background education (Figure 8), the introductory lectures were involved in the groups.

The results of the two groups are presents in the table 1, where the year indicated the plans for certain time in the future, strategies 1 and measures 1 are product of group 1, strategies 2 and measures 2 are product of group 2.

Table 1: The result performed by groups

Year	Strategies 1	Measures 1	Strategies 2	Measures 2
2020	Promotion of adopted strategies	closing of the roads for individual transport for several days,	Vegetation of riparian area Improvement of quality of living	Continuous and round cycling routes More green elements in the traffic streets More stations for Bicikel Promotion of sustainable mobility
2030	Ljubljana city for all generation	Increase of green spaces and green infrastructure with multifunctional role	Sustainable mobility Burn calories not gas	Relieve of Zois street for traffic Spread of inner pedestrian ring

				Car sharing
2050	Strategy for implementation of adopted strategies	The center of city is free of cars, the delivery is arranged	Modern, innovative city Hyper mobility, bicycle is the engine for development Work from home, reduction of needs	Complete electrification of public transport

The ideas were discussed by both groups (Figure 9). The final vision of the area of interest was to increase the traffic free zone to the wider area, to establish the sharing space which is in use on very busy area of Ljubljana, to increase the number of Bicikel (the bicycle) stations, to introduce the transport on the Ljubljanica river regular stations, to replace all public transport with electric buses and cars, to increase the number of vehicles for older and other in need (Kavalir type of individual transportation linking the public transportation). In addition, city would need to work on restoration of green areas, including new water elements (fountains and drinking water areas). Another systematic solution for cleaner air is complete public heating system which is currently not available.

7.2.5 Conclusions

The Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop (MLW) in Ljubljana took place on 15th of March 2018 on the premises of Ljubljana municipality City Hall. The workshop was attended by 15 participants from different institutions and non-governmental sectors with the aim to discuss the possibilities for improvement of air quality in the city and to decrease the health impacts for future.

The MLW was divided in two parts, first covering the theoretical findings relevant for the city and presenting some of the recent national and international projects. The second part was based on the real field tour and the question how to improve sustainable mobility in the area. The participants were innovative and discussed the possible improvement of situation, also by increasing measures which are already now available (like, pedestrian zones, share spaces, electric cars Kavalir for vulnerable individuals, Bicikel service).

But they also introduce new ideas like improvements of heat supply system to avoid the use of wood, use of river Ljubljanica for transportation and introduction of new green and water elements to be enjoyed by citizens.

The MLW provides a good tool for discussion the possible vision, strategies and measures for improvement of air quality in the city. Therefore, it is advised to be used also on regular basis by the city authority.

7.3 Sosnowiec

Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop (MLW) in Sosnowiec took place on 26th of January 2018.

7.3.1 Presentations

1. Department of Municipal Property and Environmental Management (City Hall Sosnowiec) - Anna Rączka, Tomasz Przedpełski
2. Department of Road and Traffic Management (City Hall Sosnowiec) - Robert Dworak
3. Regional Inspectorate for Environmental Protection - Lilia Szymańska-Kubicka
4. Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health - Deputy Director for Scientific Affairs PhD hab. Danuta Mielżyńska

7.3.2. Stakeholders

The composition of the participants shows the involvement of different stakeholders in the MLW, as it is proposed in the MLW Guideline (D.4.14)

Sosnowiec MLW is a good example can be a good model for the European cities/regions on how to engage stakeholders on the air quality, climate change and public health today and in the future (2020, 2030, 2050).

The Department of Municipal Property and Environmental Management, the Road and Traffic Management, Property Management (City Hall Sosnowiec), the Regional Inspectorate for Environmental Protection, The Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health, the Humanitas University, Dean of the Administration and Management Faculty, the Public Transport Company, the Silesian Trams, the Zagłębiowski Smog Alert (NGO), Municipal Waste Management Company and other civil society groups were engaged at the MLW in Sosnowiec.

7.3.2 Workshop sessions and conclusions

07.30 – 08.00 – registration

08.00 – 09.40 – presentations:

1. **Barbara Kossowska – Siwiec**, City Hall Sosnowiec – introduction to the workshop, presentation of ClairCity project; **Lilia Szymańska-Kubicka**, Regional Inspectorate for Environmental Protection: " **Air quality in Sosnowiec: past, present and future**".

Air quality in Sosnowiec and the region. Sosnowiec is one of the most polluted places in Poland and Europe. The agglomeration of Silesia, to which Sosnowiec belongs, has the worst air (several hundred percent of the exceedance of particulate matter PM 2.5 and PM 10 and benzo (a) pyrene) mainly in the cold months (late autumn - winter - spring). Pollution is caused mainly by the residents themselves by burning bad quality fuel in outdated furnaces, thus heating their homes and apartments. In the summer months the air condition is relatively good (well below

the permissible concentrations), which proves that emissions from transport and industrial activities do not have a dominant influence on the state of air in the city.

2. **Robert Dworak**, Department of Road and Traffic Management (City Hall Sosnowiec):
"Transport in Sosnowiec: past, present and future".

The city's intensive development took place in the 1970s. At that time, a road network was planned, which to a large extent functions to this day. At that time, individual road transport was the most important. Creating a network of roads convenient for drivers, giving them priority for pedestrians and cyclists was the main goal of the authorities. The road network was planned in such a way that the city is rarely dodged today and driving is easier and faster than in neighboring cities. However, the space for pedestrians and cyclists is very limited.

Currently, there is a change in the perception of urban space and more and more attention is paid to facilitating pedestrians, public transport and cyclists. This is mainly due to the assumption that expanding the road network has the opposite effect from that planned and encourages an increasing number of inhabitants to use individual cars. That's why the city decided to create the first buspas running through the city center (the main street in the city), city bike rental, new bicycle paths, transfer centers, and the plans for the near future are changing the character of the city center for pedestrian-friendly. The center's reconstruction plan is in the final phase.

3. **Anna Rączka, Tomasz Przedpełski**, Department of Municipal Property and Environmental Management (City Hall Sosnowiec):
"Energy in Sosnowiec: past, present and future"

Sosnowiec conducts a number of activities aimed at improving air quality. The city is currently focused on the modernization of heating, building insulation, expansion and modernization of heating systems and installation of renewable sources. The regional anti-smog resolution implemented in 2017 prohibits the use of poor quality fuels and obliges residents to replace old furnaces. Sosnowiec offers its residents a high co-financing for exchanging the heating method for environmentally friendly ones.

The city also implements measures aimed at energy savings: it exchanges energy-intensive street lighting for LED with an intelligent control system, and also introduces a thermal and electrical energy management system in schools.

Sosnowiec as one of the 44 Polish cities participates in a project financed from European and national funds, which will result in the development of an urban plan for adaptation to climate change. The aim of the project is to examine the vulnerability, vulnerability and resilience of the city to possible climate changes and to prepare city authorities and their residents to respond to them responsibly and responsibly.

4. **PhD hab. Danuta Mielżyńska**, Deputy Director for Scientific Affairs, Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health:
"Air quality's impact on the health of residents of Sosnowiec"

The presentation concerned the health effects caused by living in a city where air quality is low throughout the year and as a result of the so-called smog incidents.

Inhabitants of Sosnowiec, inhaling the air, have health effects similar to burning out several thousand cigarettes a year.

Diseases affect residents of all ages and vary in severity, depending on individual health characteristics. The catalog of diseases is very wide, from obvious (related to the respiratory system), to autism, diabetes, allergies, etc. Medicine has 100% proven to link certain diseases with the state of air, and science constantly adds new diseases to the existing catalog.

End of part 1.

9.40 – 10.00 – breakfast break

10.00 – 12.00 – workshop session

Part 2 of the workshop was carried out in another hall of the Municipal Office in Sosnowiec. At the beginning, the moderator of the meeting, Mrs. Barbara Kossowska-Siwiec once again explained the purpose of the meeting and its importance for the success of the ClairCity project.

All participants of the workshop received Information Cards with which they got acquainted before signing the Consent for Participation in the workshop and attendance list.

Table 1. Moderator: Edyta Wykurz

In the first part of the talks on building scenarios up to 2020, 2030 and 2050, the group had the greatest difficulty with the vision of 2050.

It was decided that by 2020 little will change. There will be the first signs of upcoming changes, but it will be a very preliminary phase. The most important changes will take place by 2030. The year 2050 is very difficult to describe, because technologies change so quickly that it is difficult to predict at the time what solutions will be considered ecological and economic at that time.

2020:

- public transport will be more ecological (almost all buses will be electric or hybrid); the tram transport will also be modernized, new tracks will be created;
- first charging stations for electric cars will be created;
- the first changes in the behavior of residents should occur, which will be the result of a better one
 - adapting the product to customer expectations;
- there will be no significant changes in the method of heating homes, there will still be many residents using poor quality fuels and burning fuels in old furnaces;
- the first inhabitants will start using renewable energy sources;
- the air quality will still be bad, in the winter months permissible pollutant concentration limits will be well above the limits;
- health effects caused by air pollution will be felt.

2030:

- public transport will not use solid fuels;
- a total ban on the use of diesel vehicles will be introduced (this will be forced by the European Union);
- the city center will be more citizen-friendly, cars will be banned from entering center;
- old stoves will be removed from homes;
- urban lighting will be completely replaced with LED;
- more green areas will be created, green buildings will appear (with greenery on the roofs and walls);
- in the city, due to population decline, many residential buildings will be abandoned.

It will be necessary to demolish them or change their functionality;

- the society will be old, there will be a need to provide new services for seniors;
- the health effects caused by air pollution will continue to be felt.

2050:

- most of the heating energy will be generated from renewable sources;
- urban lighting will be even more ecological than LED (currently unknown technology);
- the city will be definitely greener;
- public transport will develop in a difficult direction to determine;
- the health effects caused by air pollution will continue to be felt.

Barriers:

Barriers that complicate the implementation of the scenarios can be divided into three groups: legal, financial and related to the awareness of residents.

Currently, the law in Poland is not stable, it is often changing, it does not give any guarantee for the future. For this reason, people are afraid to invest in modern solutions. They are not sure that the technology, which is currently promoted and for which financial concessions are granted, will not be charged with additional fees in the near future (*legal obstacles*).

Society is too poor to bear the costs of energy transformation. Earnings of Polish residents are lower than the income of Western European citizens. Co-financing of, for example, replacement of a furnace with a modern one is not sufficient, as the cost of fuel for a new boiler is often impossible to be borne by residents (*financial obstacles*).

Society is not fully aware of the consequences of their own actions. There is no knowledge about the health consequences of burning low quality fuels or rubbish (*an obstacle related to the consciousness of residents*).

Other barriers:

- for example related to the development of bicycle communication: employers do not provide employees with adequate social conditions. The office employee should be able to shower, change clothes, store the bicycle while working;

- local government employees do not take part in trainings offered by, for example, universities increasing their knowledge about renewable energy sources;
- activity of energy companies: residents exchange lighting and home appliances for more economical, and electricity bills do not decrease. Energy companies inflate bills to keep profit.

Solutions:

- introduction of a stable, good law;
- market regulation by the national government (reduction of energy prices);
- maintaining the current subsidy for replacement of boilers and introducing co-financing to operating costs (purchase of fuels);
- permanent educational activity;
- encouraging people to green their surroundings (garden instead of parking);
- adaptation of services to the needs of an aging society;
- proper spatial planning (controlled sale of plots for development, creation of so-called green islands);
- purchase of air purifiers for public buildings (eg for nurseries, kindergartens);
- increasing the involvement of residents in activities to improve air quality.

Table 2. Moderator: Ewa Karaban

The group discussed the vision of Sosnowiec's development in three perspectives: by 2010, 2030 and 2050. At the beginning of the discussion, it was noted that it was impossible to build a strategy for Sosnowiec in isolation from the region. One of the discussion participants was a member of the board of the Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis - an institution responsible for creating a common policy of cities, including in the field of transport.

The group decided that the 2020 perspective will be the time of implementing already initiated measures and possibly new solutions. "Revolutionary" changes can take place in the next decade. The most difficulties were caused by the year 2050 as the most distant, difficult to predict, perspective.

2020:

- Transfer centers will be created.
- Car free zones will be introduced
- Banning of poor quality fuels.

- Subsidies to change the way of heating to more eco-friendly will be sustained.
- More greenery in the city.
- Free public transport for some social groups.
- Educational campaigns that raise the environmental awareness of residents.

2030:

- Replacement of heat sources throughout the city for low-emission.
- Community (group of residents) heating networks will be created.
- Waste will be treated not as garbage, but as resources that can be used for energy purposes.
- Car traffic in the city will be significantly reduced, favoring pedestrians and cyclists.
- Cheaper, better public transport (more connections).
- Passive buildings will be more popular.
- Better spatial planning - more greenery will appear in public and private spaces

2050:

- Individual household power plants will be built.
- Energy will be obtained mainly from renewable sources (sun, wind) and from waste (thus the problem of landfilling will be completely eliminated).
- Car traffic will be significantly reduced due to the lack of frequent movement of residents (they will work in homes - teleworking).
- Only electric and hydrogen cars will move along the streets.
- New energy and transport technologies will be implemented.
- City - a garden with lots of greenery.

Barriers:

The basic barriers to the full implementation of the scenarios concern financial limitations and the residents' awareness. For inhabitants, the financial balance is important, both in the case of transport (moving by car is faster and cheaper) and heating homes (it is still cheaper to use coal than using ecological fuels). The introduction of new solutions in the field of thermal energy (considered by the group as the most important) can be a big problem especially for the poorest social groups.

Other barriers:

- Ownership of the land and spatial and climatic conditions will make it difficult to design a garden city and introduce more greenery.
- Current legal regulations prevent the full use of waste as a source of energy.
- Aging society, social resistance and architectural barriers will not allow complete elimination of car traffic in the city center.

Solutions:

- Additional sources of financing for exchanging the heating method and introducing renewable energy sources.
- Priority given by national, regional and local authorities to pro-ecological activities.
- Conducting public consultations, actions raising the health awareness of residents and a clear indication of the benefits of pro-ecological solutions.
- New municipal (ecological) housing.
- Ban on the sale of coal.
- Better planning of space in the city.
- Co-financing from employers for public transport for employees.
- Relevant legal regulations.
- Attempt to overcome architectural barriers.

Table 3. Moderator: Barbara Grzebulska, REC Poland.

Thanks to the participation of people involved in the development of urban transport in the discussion, the group had information about the state of progress of the projects initiated regarding the modernization of electric urban transport or the construction of bicycle paths. The vision of changes in the upcoming 2020 perspective has not created problems for the group.

Visions of development prospects until 2030 and 2050 after the initial brainstorm were also coherently outlined. Interestingly, the group unanimously noted that by 2050 a world-view revolution is needed that would discourage the consumption of society and the sense of a greater bond and responsibility of the individual. The discussion also included observations that in a demographically aging society, seniors are a very important target group of all projects and educational activities. There was also a voice in the conversation that these days it is a neglected group in educational and promotional activities

2020:

- public health education (using antismog masks)
- seniors' education
- connecting to the municipal heating network of buildings
- actions for the growth of renewable energy through the creation of new funding mechanisms
- replacement of boilers for new type boilers (5th class)
- building a mechanism for financing new boilers
- introduction of legislation regarding the ban on placing solid non-fossil fuels on the market

- City Social Assistance Center could buy better quality coal
- development of green areas
- construction of transfer centers
- construction of bicycle paths and bike rental networks
- modernization of the tram network
- development of electric bus networks
- improving access to information for the residents

2030:

- public transport
- cars excluded from the city center (except for electric cars)
- heating centers - development and connection of all excluded buildings
- moving people to city centers
- modernization of historic buildings (connection to heating networks and energy efficiency)
- a command and relief tool needed to pressure the connection of new buildings to the heating network
- development of photovoltaics, wind energy and heat pumps
- increased green areas
- ban on capping green areas
- appropriate provisions in urban spatial development plans for buildings (connection to the network and thermo-modernization) and green areas
- revitalization of space

2050:

- total reconstruction of green areas
- establishing the continuity of the blue and green infrastructure networks

- total abandonment of fossil fuel energy
- total elimination of individual carbon sources
- all houses subjected to thermo-modernization, new built houses only passive
- Seniors should be exempted from fees for the use and implementation of green infrastructure

Barriers:

At the same time, workshop participants tried to provide ideas for solving the barrier. As a result, many new ideas appeared that seem to be feasible.

- low public awareness of health threats, downplaying the impact of smog on health
- mental barrier
- insufficient financial support for anti-smog resolution solutions
- the need to strengthen social bonds
- lack of education regarding the impact on health
- difficulty in operating new furnaces
- no legislation on the quality of solid fuels
- no law enforcement difficulties
- no quality standards for fuel
- no penalties for burning low-quality fuel
- administrative barriers regarding renewable energy sources
- a problem with the adjustment of low-floor rolling stock
- no charging station for electric cars
- a problem with social acceptance of changes concerning the use of personal cars

Solutions:

- pre-school, school and seniors education (awareness must increase at every stage)
- using municipal events to promote ecological solutions

- creating a help system and advice for users, eg new boilers
- eco-radar system
- information on exceedances
- the system of co-financing changes combined with unavoidable financial penalties
- Improvision of law enforcement for all types of emissions (low emissions, industrial emissions, energy)
- changes in the law regarding the possibility of conducting emergency inspections by Voivodship Inspectorates for Environmental Protection
- public health as a priority at the government level
- lifestyle change for less consumption
- a change in the philosophy of life
- construction of sustainable zero-emission solutions - secondary use of raw materials
- creating exchange points for goods
- no fees for seniors for pro-ecological solutions
- elevation of the stops (adaptation of the public transport fleet - low floors)

In the second part of the meeting, between two rounds of discussions, the moderator invited all participants to participate in the "**Mood in the Room**" (10-minute energizer).

Three theses were put forward before the participants for conclusion:

1. "In 2030, there will be no individual cars in the center of Sosnowiec".
2. "Introduction of a total ban on using coal as fuel in households would have a significant impact on air quality and our health".
5. "Entry into force of the "anti-smog resolution" (Resolution No. V / 36/1/2017 of the Śląskie Regional Assembly of April 7, 2017 on the introduction of restrictions on the operation of installations in which the fuel is burned) which will result in a significant reduction of "low emissions" in the cities of our region".

The workshop participants who agreed with the thesis were asked to take a seat on the right side of the room, while its opponents stood on the left side.

In the case of **thesis No. 1**, the majority of participants strongly agreed with it. The representative of the opponents group, when asked why he considers the thesis impossible, explained that in his opinion, the use of personal cars for official purposes would be exercised on special rights by people holding public functions working in public buildings located in the city center.

All participants of the workshop agreed with the **thesis No. 2**.

In the case of **thesis No. 3**, only 3 people claimed that it was true. The comment of a representative of this small group, however, indicated the need to introduce in Poland legal provisions regulating the issues raised in the "anti-smog resolution" at the national level. The vast majority of participants were opposed. The representative of this group, asked to explain this position, stated that without increasing the awareness of all residents, despite the legal regulations, the use of highly harmful fuels and even rubbish will still take place.

7.4 Aveiro region

The Aveiro Region (CIRA) MLW was held on the 28th of February 2018 during the afternoon, from 14:00 to 17:30, at the Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro.

7.4.1 Participants and logistics

Participants from different municipal and regional organizations (NGO's) on mobility, environment and health and governmental entities as the regional directorates of environment and health were invited by the city partner CIRA. The participants list can be found in Annex I.

Two rooms were used, one for the plenary section and other for the group activities. Prior to the meeting, the tables were organized for group work, the posters were posted and materials were put on the tables. For the working group sessions, a series of power point slides were prepared and presented, aiming to help the moderator to explain the tasks and the participants to better understand what they were asked to do at each step.

Myriam Lopes, the Portuguese coordinator of ClairCity, moderated the workshop, and a group of team members (from UAVR and CIRA) helped as facilitators and as room helping staff:

Facilitators	Room staff (pictures and materials)	Materials
Vera Rodrigues, UAVR	Sara Silva, UAVR	Participant sign-up sheet
Sílvia Coelho, UAVR	Carlos Faria, UAVR	Participant information sheets
Joana Ferreira, UAVR		Consent forms
Olgra Cravo, CIRA		Large posters for: - Aveiro Region 2020 - Aveiro Region 2030, challenges and barriers - Aveiro Region 2050
		Ppt slide presentation
		Pens, stickers, post-it notes, paper

The agenda of the Aveiro Region Mutual Learning Workshop was based on the MLW guidelines and adapted to the Portuguese habits and time schedules. The MLW started by a Plenary Session, preceded by a short Welcoming and introduction, and followed by the working group tasks and discussion divided in three parts. The following section describe in more detail the activities performed and the main topics of discussion and conclusions.

7.4.2 Agenda

13:45	Arrival and sign in
14:00 Start	
14:00	Welcome (Myriam Lopes and José Eduardo de Matos)
14:10	Plenary session
	Carlos Borrego (DAO-UA) – “Air Quality in the Aveiro Region”
	Margarida Coelho (DEM-UA) – “Connected, Intelligent and Sustainable Mobility: the link between Scientific research and Transport Policies”
	Discussion
15:00	Working Group I – Actions and scenarios
	Visions 2020
	Visions 2050
16:00 Coffee break	
16:15	Working Group II
	Challenges and barriers
	Actions, milestones and priorities
16:55	Feedback from groups and discussion
	Policies, strategies and actions – Visions 2020 to 2050
17:15	Conclusions/ closing words
17:30 End	

7.4.3 Welcome

The welcoming to the University of Aveiro and an introduction to the ClairCity project and the MLW goal was given by Myriam Lopes with the support of a few ppt slides. The Executive Secretary of CIRA, José Eduardo Matos, acknowledged the presence of the participants and highlighted the importance of this type of initiatives for the development of the region.

Participants were asked to read the information sheet and sign the consent form and the list of participants.

7.4.4 Plenary Session

The aim of the plenary was to give an overview of the air pollution problems in the Aveiro Region and to present past and ongoing research on methods to improve air quality, human comfort and wellbeing and protect human health. For that, Carlos Borrego (full professor at the Dept Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro) and Margarida Coelho (Assistant Professor at the Dept of Mechanical Engineer, University of Aveiro) were invited. Carlos Borrego gave a brief introduction to the subject and presented some case studies where modelling tools were applied to test measures (influence of trees, route options, ...) to improve air quality, reduce human exposure and increase human comfort. Margarida Coelho introduced her research group of Transportation Technology and its main fields of research, the concept of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and Advanced Transport Mobility Systems (ATMS). She presented the aims and expected outcomes of three ongoing projects. The @CRUiSE: Advanced Impact Integration Platform for Cooperative Road Use, includes a mobile app, a GIS model with noise, emissions and costs data, and an On-Board Platform of Sensors for Enhancing Safety of Cyclists; the project MobiWise: from mobile sensing to mobility advising aiming to design a 5G platform with an infrastructure of sensors, people and vehicles and data storage in a cloud; and the project CISMob dealing with the mobility challenges in the Aveiro Region promoting innovative actions to reduce the carbon footprint and aiming to increasing sustainability by a better efficient use of urban transport infrastructures.

After the talks, there was time for a general discussion on the topics addressed by the speakers.

After the Plenary Session, participants were invited to move to the other room and sit in groups of 4 or 5 people around each table with a facilitator.

7.4.5 Working Group I

Before starting each participant presented himself and the entity he was representing. The team members (facilitators and helpers) were also introduced to the whole group.

Description

Myriam Lopes presented the first activity - Actions and Scenarios - Visions for the year 2020 in the Aveiro Region. Within their group, each participant was invited to present the material brought about actions that contribute to the environment and health in the region. Since just one or two participants brought a leaflet, the facilitator encourage participants to share in the group the contribution of their organization to make the Region of Aveiro healthier, with a cleaner air and smaller carbon footprint, in the present/ near future.

Participants with the facilitator's help put their ideas in post-it and stack in Poster 2020.

The second part of this working group I was the reflection on the visions for 2050. Each participant had to think on their visions and strategies for the future, set goals to achieve by 2050, present and discuss them within the group, and wrote them down in post-it to stick in Poster 2050.

Visions 2020 and 2050

For 2020 the main visions and ideas discussed for the Aveiro region were related to:

- the need of awareness for teachers (to engage children and parents), politicians, citizens,
- the use of IT platforms,
- improve the air quality network and monitoring of indoor air quality,
- the promotion of strategies for environment and health protection, namely promote the use of bicycles / bike paths, less cars, electric public transportations, create green corridors / forests, to guarantee emission reduction and energy and resources efficiency.

Regarding the horizon of 2050, participants were more ambitious. Their ideas cover the following aspects:

- citizenship / commitment / behaviour / values
- increase inspection
- city maps of air quality
- more efficient housing / fireplace certification
- better public transport network combined with parking outside city center, car sharing, ban car traffic in cities, create free public transport network, throughout the region, zero emission zones towards resilient cities.

More detailed information on the ideias proposed by each group is summarised in Annex II.

Before sharing the ideas proposed by each group, a coffee-break was provided. During the coffee break participants were encouraged to observe the posters, read the visions of the other groups, and reflect on the following questions:

- Is it realistic to achieve the goals set for 2050?
- Will it involve major changes?

7.4.6 Working Group II

Back to the groups, a round through the four groups was carried out aiming to share with all participants the ideas and visions of each group. Based on this presentation and on the questions raised before the break, the subsequent tasks were explained by Myriam Lopes.

Description

This second working group activity consisted of two parts. In the first part, participants were asked to think about the main challenges and barriers to reach the goals and ambitions posted for 2050 and write them in post-its. Then, to overcome the identified challenges and barriers, participants had to propose actions and strategies to be implemented in 2030 and prioritize them. Those actions were written in post-it with a different colour and posted next to the corresponding challenge/barrier.

Challenges and barriers – actions and priorities

Once again, participants had the opportunity to share their proposals with the others. The main challenges and barriers identified were:

- Need to change mentality / lack of individual awareness, ignorance
- Promote participation and opinion of citizens
- Fight against car lobby and energy, capitalism
- willingness to change and improve / resistance to change, egocentrism, fear
- lack of good environmental leadership/ inadaptability of policies / functioning of local policy systems
- lack of incentives for cleaner behavior and public participation / tax incentives

More details on the actions and priorities proposed, presented and discussed by each group can be found in Annex.

7.4.7 Summary and closing words

Myriam Lopes closed the workshop with a wrap up of the main ideas discussed and acknowledge the collaboration, interest and motivation of all participants.

The details of visioning Aveiro region on 2020-2030-2050 are in the Annex below.

At the end of the session participants were encourage to keep following the project news and participating in the upcoming activities, and were offered a Claircity postcard as a souvenir.

7.4.8 Annex –Group contributions to the proposed activities

Activity	Group 1	Group 2
Visions 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion, from kindergarten to high school, of educational programs and projects, actions, events, on sustainable development (mobility, energy efficiency, eco-schools, environmental management of schools, awareness of food waste, forests, noise, ...) • alerts on social media and online platforms about the environment based on complaints or events • PLeaflet about the project "Santo Cabeço" (project created after a major fire occurrence, aims to restore and protect the remaining native vegetation in a small town of Agueda - Belazaima do Chão) • regional development projects under the national environmental education strategy and national strategy for air • CCDR-C has an ongoing project called "better air in the center" which aims to improve the air quality network for more and better information on the air quality in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a company in Gafanha da Nazaré that promotes the use of bicycles giving an extra day of annual leave for those who bike to work • By 2020, it is planned to create 30 km of cycle paths in Ílhavo • 300 students from Gafanha da Nazaré use the bike daily. Project: "The future of cities is the bicycle" aims to replace the car by the bike • Entrepreneurship competition (increase the number of projects related to the quality of the bicycles) • C MARKET (from 2012, 2013): awareness-raising for the reduction of carbon footprint, more efficient processes and energy efficiency certification • Proposal presented to the City Hall to provide bicycles, allowing mobility between services • Leaflet of project UAU BIKE.PT. Provision of bikes to the academic community (teachers, students and staff) to increase the use of bicycles instead of the car
Visions 2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • absence of car parking in the center of urban areas • free network of electric buses or other public transports, throughout the region • tree planting in the cities and adjacent areas; creation of ecological corridors • no tolls on the A25 / A17 sections • network bike lanes across the region • creation of incentives for transport sharing (car, bike, boat sharing) • people commit to promote the sustainability of the planet and to contribute for the quality of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prohibit the circulation of private cars in cities, car parks in the peripheral areas • parking for bicycles/ safe infrastructures • rental of hybrid and electric cars • micro-cars / bicycles, "cool" bicycles • transport sharing • best electric public transport network (density, frequency and schedules) • certification of fireplaces • more efficient housing • more infrastructures prepared for cyclists in public services and companies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inform people enabling them to opt for sustainable mobility, efficient use of houses and efficient use of resources, value the preservation of the environment • more enforcement to ensure compliance with environmental legislation • incentives for the use of cleaner technologies • environmental awareness 	
<p>2030 – Challenges and Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capitalism - financial economy based on debt • fear and egocentrism, ignorance, lack of leadership and lack of will • lack of participative processes at community level, lack of policy makers with environmental conscience • lack of incentives for more sustainable behaviours (use of bikes, walking and car sharing) • willingness to improve; • need of greater involvement and better supervision; • more and better information for full awareness of reality; • good environmental leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mentality • land use/urban planning • participation and opinion of citizens • education and awareness • resistance to change • information and communication • fight against car and energy lobby
<p>2030 – Actions and Priorities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • alternative means of exchange, instead of using money • environmental awareness - the need to link health to the environment • invite the community to implement strategies, to take action and to monitor • press policy-makers for change • for more environmental monitoring: government guidelines with guaranteed involvement of more human and financial resources • education/ valorization of the essential role of each one in the promotion of behaviours that promote the sustainability of the planet and the quality of life (priority 1) • Promote awareness on sustainable mobility, energy efficiency, resource use and other that lead to environmental friendly decisions (priority 2) • education for citizenship and exercise civic participation (involving students, families, communities) (priority 3) • promote opportunities for active participation in the education for sustainability. Each person contribute to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • marketing • strategic vision for planning • certification of cities ("child-friendly city") • invest on information and awareness programs • more open school curricula • goals: establish the results to be achieved, with measurable goals

	his own sustainable development (priority 4)	
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Activity	Group 3	Group 4
Visions 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pedagogy to the community, better conditions/ public policy pressure • reduce car use /increase bicycle use • Measures to reduce particulate emissions in port activity, evaluation of air quality in Gafanha da Nazaré; • Air quality information to the population • energy efficiency measures • support to University of Aveiro studies on air quality or health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implement a plan towards low carbon emissions, considering water, energy and waste • implement measures of energy efficiency (namely in transport sector), and efficient use of resources • monitor and assess indoor air quality (particularly in health services), including the definition of control measures to prevent exposure • raise awareness of workers and users of health services, politicians and citizens in general for environment and health related problems • monitor atmospheric emissions of point sources (related with health services emissions) and verify legal compliance • promote research, through financial grants, related with health and exposure to environmental key factors

<p>Visions 2050</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • renew the bus fleet using cleaner technology and introduce new electric bus in Aveiro region public transportation network • Supervise the industrial activity
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-polluting cars; • more and better legislation; • cities that are more sustainable, more resilient and closer to the citizen; • educated, more informed and more responsible citizen; • Efficient public transport network; • car-sharing; • increased use of pedestrian and cycling modes; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of private cars in cities • Proactive identification of pollution problems – diseases, indicators • Contact with nature (e.g. to understand and follow the food lifecycle) • Knowledge and education (need to know the planet to protect it), training and information • Integrated mobility policies, complementary modes (e.g. private car – bus – bike), efficient public transportation network • Return the city to citizens • Effective assessment of the cause-effect between diseases/ morbidity/ mortality and exposure to air pollution • Implement protective strategies – reduction of exposure (e.g. domestic, workplace, urban environments) • Municipal air quality maps as a decision-support system to include in urban planning • Urban road traffic management depending on AQ monitoring in real time, considering innovative tools of AQ monitoring and modelling.
<p>2030 – Challenges and Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of individual consciousness; • change mentality; • economic interests of the car industry; • educate citizen and politicians; • function of political power; • change the way you act; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • hard to change implemented habits and recognize the need to change, inertia • easier to think individually • Mismatch between citizens and the overall politicians • lack of financial support of individual citizens in their sustainable choices (e.g. non-pollutant equipment or with low-emissions, change from private car to bike use) • lack of connection between citizens and nature, lack of knowledge about environmental issues

2030 –
Actions and
Priorities

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • include in the programmatic content of the citizenship discipline concerns about air quality, health and carbon footprint (priority 1); • train politicians: create a proximity committee between university/ municipalities / citizens (priority 2); • prohibit the circulation of cars (mainly diesel), creating support structures (priority 3); • promote more efficient heating equipment (priority 4) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promote knowledge transfer between distinct sectors, disseminate knowledge and information • promote changes in citizens behaviour • define priorities that will promote shared mobility (e.g. public bus) • include air quality as a goal of the national policy program, including financial funds available to support that. • integrate effective measures within governance strategies at community and national levels • create urban planning management strategies oriented through citizens (e.g. smartphones app's for sharing of mobility solutions, efficient use of urban resources, strategies to improve and preserve well-being and lifestyle) • increase citizens' contact with environmental practices • link again citizens and nature in order to raise awareness on nature protection and preservation • raise awareness about climate change effects within CIRA, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, remediate – planning for more extreme weather events • perform environmental monitoring and assessment, including the implementation of more air quality stations • improve sustainable mobility, urban planning strategies, home-school-work-leisure accessibilities, promote non-pollutant public transportation. |
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7.5 Liguria region

This MLW took place on 27 March 2018.

7.5.1 Workshop Information

Team of facilitators

Moderator:

Cecilia Brescianini (General Vice - Director Liguria Region)

Facilitators:

Carlo Trozzi (Techne Consulting)

Rita Vaccaro (Techne Consulting)

Patrizia Costi (Liguria Region)

Angela Patrone ((Liguria Region)

Carlotta Ghirardo ((Liguria Region)

Gabor Heves (REC)

Participants

We had a total of 35 participants, 28 excluding the moderator and the facilitators. The participants represented various departments of the Region (health, energy, transport), of the City of Genoa (health, transport) and of its territorial structures (municipalities), the Regional Energy Agency, private companies, Port authority, Regional Environmental Agency, NGOs, Health and Environmental Agencies.

Location & Agenda

Date: 27 March 2018

Place: Liguria Region, Via Fieschi 16131, Genoa

7.5.2 Agenda

09:00 Arrivo e registrazione (Accoglienza Caffè)

Inizio

- 09:20 **Saluto** Assessore Giampedrone
- 09:30 **Politiche sulle Qualità dell'aria** – Dott.ssa Brescianini (Vice Direttore Generale Regione Liguria)
- 09:40 **Introduzione e descrizione del progetto** - Dr. Trozzi (Progetto ClairCity, Techne Consulting)
- 09:50 **Relazione speaker 1** – Dr. Campora (Comune di Genova, Assessore all'Ambiente e Rifiuti)

Politiche ambientali e attività per la riduzione e gestione dell'inquinamento atmosferico, con scenari al 2020 e 2030 e visione futura al 2050 - ASSENTE

- 10:10 **Relazione speaker 2** – Dott.ssa Fabianelli (Direttore della Divisione Energia IRE S.p.A.). Pianificazione, Efficienza e Gestione energetica.
- 10:30 **Relazione speaker 3** – Dr. Merella (Regione Liguria) Settore infrastrutture
- 10:50 **Relazione speaker 4** – Dott.ssa Nicosia (Regione Liguria) Settore Tutela della salute negli ambienti di vita e di lavoro
- 11:10 **Relazione speaker 5** – Dr. Balleari (Comune di Genova, Vice Sindaco - Assessore alla Mobilità e Trasporto Pubblico locale).
- Politiche relative alla mobilità, alla logistica e al trasporto pubblico, con scenari al 2020 e 2030 e visione futura al 2050.

11:30: Break

- 11.45 **Tavola Rotonda:** Scenari al 2020 e 2030, Visioni al 2050
- 12:15 **Dibattito:** Sfide, politiche, strategie, azioni e soluzioni
- 12.45 **Conclusioni/ considerazioni finali** (Gabor Heves, REC, Progetto ClairCity)

13.00 Fine delle attività

7.5.3 Welcome and introduction

Policies on air quality by Mrs. Cecilia Brescianini (Liguria Region, Deputy Director-General)

After the presentation of the ClairCity project, Mrs. Brescianini underlined the general goals of the ClairCity MLW meeting.

Next Dr Brescianini describes the air quality situation in Region.

In Liguria, despite significant improvements in air quality, problems persist with regard to pollutants NO₂ and O₃, particularly in the agglomeration of Genoa, of interest for the ClairCity project.

In the specific case of Genoa, the pollutant that raises the most concern is nitrogen dioxide, for exceeding the annual average limit in city monitoring stations located in

areas of heavy road traffic, and ozone. The values of PM₁₀ generally respect the limits, although exceedances can occur as happened in 2015 in particular climatic conditions. In Genoa, air quality is therefore a problem for the health of citizens.

The causes of this situation can be identified by analysing the emission sources and the distribution of concentrations. The main sources of PM₁₀ and NO_x emissions in the city of Genoa are the port and the road traffic. The main contribution to the local level of NO₂ and PM₁₀ concentrations recorded by the monitoring stations of the regional air quality network located in the urban areas of Genoa is determined by road traffic.

The Region under the national law has the task of adopting the plans and measures necessary to reduce the concentrations within the limits or objectives established by the national and European standard. As a consequence of the exceeding of the limits for nitrogen dioxide, an infringement procedure is underway with the European Commission.

Climate change, an environmental aspect of a global nature, is important for Liguria and Genoa for the local effects it produces (increased risk of phenomena of hydrogeological instability, drought and fire, heat waves) with consequent effects on people, their health and on the economy. Therefore, the integration between the objectives of air quality improvement and the objectives of reducing greenhouse gas emissions is strongly necessary.

The Deputy Director Environment of the Liguria Region is planning the drafting of the Action Plan, which will include:

- An overview of the measures already taken by local and regional administrations,
- Urgent additional measures to reduce the concentration of pollutants in the ambient air,
- Provision for monitoring the effects of the action plan,
- Communication and information to the public.

The short-term measures that will be assessed with the involvement of the Administrations involved, concern:

- Measures to regulate urban road traffic such as: limit circulation to the most polluting vehicles, traffic management in particular critical situations such as large construction sites work interfering with city traffic, agreement with Port Authority for the management of traffic linked to port accesses, regulation of accesses to motorways, regulation of distribution of goods in urban areas
- Measures on the use of Biomass such as selective incentives, better knowledge.

The long-term measures will be foreseeing in the urban mobility plans, as an important tool that can contribute to the reduction of the use of private vehicles, and o the electric mobility while with regard to emissions from maritime activities that are generally of a

"over regional" nature, the Region intends to set up a discussion table with the Port Authorities.

Last but not least is the information, to start creating awareness on the topic, and for this reason the ClairCity project will make a great contribution.

Introduction and description of the project

by Mr. Carlo Trozzi (ClairCity, project, Techne Consulting)

A brief presentation about ClairCity project, its objectives, partners, WPs with particular reference to WP4 (Engagement citizens and stakeholders) was made explaining the scope of the Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW).

It was explained how ClairCity has the ambition to create an important change in the behaviour of the citizens toward the causes of the scarce air quality, inviting the citizens to express their opinions about the air pollution and carbon footprint reduction in order to modelling the city of the future.

It was presented the innovative instruments to quantify the pollution and increase the awareness of the citizens through their involvement in the definition of a set of future scenarios for emissions reductions, minimize the impact on the health and supporting the development of policy measures with a vision to 2050.

The involvement of the citizens and of the stakeholders is carried out through Delphi Process (2 questionnaires and 2 workshop), an App, a Game, MLW, school competition, City day), using social media and a website for the information dissemination.

Regarding the MLW in Genoa, different stakeholders involved in environmental and health issues have been invited to participate. To the participants is asked to share the vision on the risk factors of their city at actual and future scenarios (2020-2030-2050).

All the activities developed in Liguria region were briefly presented, particularly about questionnaires (R1 and R2, Delphi Workshop, interviews to different stakeholders (Public Administrators, Energy and environmental agencies representatives, Port Authority representatives, Members of environmental organizations)

7.5.4 Keynotes

Speaker 1:

Mrs. Maria Fabianelli (Director of the Division Energy of IRE S.p.A.)

IRE S.p.A., is a company of the Region that deals with infrastructures, building renovation and energy.

The presentation introduced the planning framework with the European and national context, the Regional Environmental Energy Plan 2014-2020, and the local context with the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. Following the innovative financial instruments for energy efficiency (EPC, ELENA, Horizon 2020, etc.) and the activities of management of supply and maintenance contracts for hospitals have been mentioned.

The new Regional Environmental Energy Plan (PEAR 2014-2020), approved on 2017, constitutes the strategic instrument for the regional energy planning of the civil sector (residential + tertiary + public) alone is responsible for about 50% of regional final consumption and sets targets and actions on energy efficiency and renewable sources in Liguria, incorporating the contents of national «Burden Sharing» legislation which assigns to each region the targets for 2020.

Mrs. Fabianelli focused on energy information system of Liguria Region. For many years the Liguria Region has been the only Region in Italy to elaborate and maintain a Regional Energy Balance, using original regional data, thanks to the regional information system, in synergy with the emission inventory. This information is elaborated at regional level also using direct census on main energy producers and consumers as well as transport infrastructures.

In the frame of Covenant of Mayors municipalities commit to reduce their emissions by 20% by 2020 developing a Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP). Andora in Liguria region has been the first municipality that has joined. In 2015 the Covenant of Mayor

for Climate and Energy was launched, thus incorporating the issues related to adaptation to climate change. The document that the municipalities must draft is now called Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate (SECAP). IRE supports the preparation of SEAP / SECAP in Liguria realizing a large number of SEAP (including the Municipality of Savona and the Municipality of Genoa) and is involved in some new SECAP including those of Sanremo, Genoa and Savona.

Finally, IRE forwards works in agreement with the Region on the Elena program (EC program supports local actors on large scale energy efficiency investments projects and covers 90% of costs) and on horizon2020 programming.

Speaker 2:

Mr. Arcangelo Merella (Liguria Region, Infrastructure Sector)

The speaker evidenced as the high willingness to the use of private vehicles, the concentration of major part of population in urban areas and the inadequacy of public transport produce a large volume of traffic in the cities.

The average times of travels are always higher and therefore it is necessary to implement a more integrated approach for cities planning, the city planning must be integrated with transport planning.

Undoubtedly in the cities, also in Genoa, environmental benefits can come from the reduction of transport costs connected to the use of individual transports and therefore it is important to act on the individual behaviours. In the meantime, environmental and social benefits can derive from the in-vehicles technology, reducing for example traffic congestion, travel times.

New investments are necessary for electric mobility. The charging stations are 4207 in all the national territory, about 20 in Genoa, while in Germany they are 22.000 and in UK 14.000.

Each territory has own peculiarities, so each tool has to adequate to the territory, taking into account that the good things at now, will be not valid in the future and that is fundamental the cultural aspect and the development of awareness by citizens. The theme of sustainable mobility needs to be done using a great courage and involves great change in the behaviours of the citizens.

Speaker 3:

Mrs. Elena Nicosia (Liguria Region, Department of Health and Social Services)

Environmental factors affecting health are many, but until now there have been few predictive studies, as it is very difficult to indicate the direct relationship between pathology and environmental factor.

Actually, also in Italy and in Liguria Region it's starting to work with synergy between who works on environment and who works in health, because until now environmental politics didn't preoccupy about prevention of the health.

In the National Plan of Prevention 2014/2018, macro-areas area with specific actions are introduced, like the macro-area 2.8, where are included actions to Reduce environmental exposures potentially harmful to health. One of the most important instrument is the VIS (Health Impact Assessment).

As foreseen by the State Regions Memorandum of Understanding of 2014, all the Regions and have drawn up their own Regional Prevention Plan (PRP).

The Programme II "Health and well-being" of the Liguria Regional Plan of Prevention 2014-2018 in the Macro objective "MO8: Reducing environmental exposures potentially harmful to health" includes the following actions:

- The establishment of a renewed Regional Health - Environment Observatory,
- regional guidelines for integrated health impact assessment (VIS) (DGR 1695/2016);
- Definition of regional criteria for the management of health problems attributable to environmental pollution;
- Transposition of national guidelines for risk communication or, in their absence, adoption of regional guidelines on the matter;
- Networking among all institutional subjects of environmental monitoring data and health data on mortality, incidence of neoplasia, hospitalization and reproductive outcomes, collected on the territory;
- Certification of the Animal Cancer Registry;
- Feasibility analysis on the extension of the Cancer Liguria Registry to the entire Regional population;

- Continuation of epidemiological studies initiated in particular areas at risk for environmental pollution (Savonese areas, Val Bormida and La Spezia and the marine environment);
- Definition of training curriculum for health and environment operators involved in the VIS and in the management of health problems attributable to environmental pollution;
- Promotion actions to facilitate access to public funding dedicated to information and training activities on the management of health issues attributable to environmental pollution;
- I level training (trainers) and II level (local operators) on VIS and management of health problems attributable to environmental pollution;
- Participation in the Radon National Plan for the reduction of the risk of lung cancer and the elaboration of Regional Addresses for the adoption of municipal building regulations in an eco-compatible way.

Speaker 4:

Mr. Stefano Balleari (Municipality of Genoa, deputy Major)

The deputy Major of Genoa Municipality said that they are preparing the urban plan of the sustainable mobility. In Genoa city a real planning wasn't implemented, many fragmented measures have been implemented without a global vision. The implementation of the urban plan that goes together with the transport plan is a very complex process.

At the beginning of this month the following strategic lines have been presented and started the audit of the stakeholders:

- The orientation toward the citizens should be non-sanctioning, but rewarding towards the citizens which have virtuous behavior;
- The connection between West and East zones is one of the priorities of the Municipality; in the zone of Val Polcevera an extension of the metro toward West is planned;
- In Genoa the different types of transports, railway, boat, metro (much limited) must be valorised;
- Policies related to mobility, logistics and public transport, railway, road and underground planning, regulation and management of sustainable mobility, with scenarios for 2020 and 2030 and future vision for 2050 have to be carried out;
- Incentives for a sustainable mobility must be improved (electric bus, electric cars, car pooling, bike sharing with electrically assisted pedal bicycles).
- In some years the electric vehicles charging stations should become 500 (now they are about 20).

- An issue to be solved is that of batteries because they are too much big and in the future they should be smaller with more speed charge.
- In this vision the protected buses lanes should be implemented. At present the protected yellow lane of Europa road is the unique existing protected lane in Genoa. It exists for 20 years and is particularly appreciated from the citizens because the service is faster and they have the certainty to arrive to a specific location at an appointed hour.

Welcome

by Mr. Giacomo Raul Giampedrone (Liguria Region, Assessor)

The Assessor emphasises that the theme of the project is fundamental within the Regional environmental policies. The work developed until now has been very effective, the communication and education on environmental field are very important.

The territory of Liguria Region and Genoa is very fragile but also very nice and it is important to protect it. Liguria region has in charge all air quality monitoring stations managed before by metropolitan City of Genoa.

From the point of view of air quality, Liguria team in the project has involved the citizens disseminating information on this theme, and the political structure must incorporate the indications emerged by this important project.

The councillor underlined as the Liguria region technical staff makes a good work on the theme of air quality and as also this project is a confirmation of that. For this reason, the Assessor thanked them and all the participants to MLW.

Welcome

by Mr. Antonio Piersanti (ENEA)

ENEA supports Ministry for Environment in energy scenarios processing to 2020-2030 and national air pollution scenarios the National Energy strategy, started in 2013 and becoming the official strategy. Regarding air pollution in Italy, the most critical situation

is in Po Valley, particularly for PM_{2.5}, that is very dangerous for the health. In Genoa the situation of PM_{2.5} is good, but it is not so for ozone and nitrogen oxides.

The representative of ENEA underlined that the local policies must be connected to the national policy. He also underlined the importance of national investments in infrastructures which reflect the local level (for example the electric vehicles).

7.5.5 Panel discussion

The speakers and some other participants have discussed on the theme of air quality and carbon footprint in Genoa, its policy measures, evidencing as they have to be integrated with the aspects of energy, transport and health.

An outcome of this discussion is that the work of the technicians should involve the citizens and that the politicians should incorporate the instances by citizens themselves and take into account the results of the work by technicians, including projects such as ClairCity.

7.5.6 Debate sessions

Challenges, opportunities, solutions; Policies, strategies and actions

The participants appreciated the initiative of MLW, as emerged by the evaluation forms filled by them.

Some of them underlined the necessity to connect the scientific and technical activities on these themes with the needs of the citizens.

It was particularly appreciated the tentative to put together different stakeholders permitting to deal several aspects connected to air quality theme (energy, transport, health).

Presentation

by Mr. Davide Sciutto (Western Ligurian Sea Port Authority)

Mr Sciutto presented the projects implemented and in progress and invited the participants to go near the windows of the room to see the port of Genoa (there is very nice view of the city and of the port) while he described the three projects.

The first project consists in electrifying fourteen moorings in the area of naval repairs. This project will allow us to switch off the generators on board the ships being repaired. The project has a cost of about 12 million-euro co financed by the Ministry of Environment and the Liguria region. The project carried out by the Enel energy company.

The second project is to electrify the port of Voltri - Pra in order to be able to feed container ships during the loading - unloading of containers. These ships are already prepared for connection to a ground electric system. We have already on the agenda some inspections on board these ships to define the technical aspects that the system on the ground must meet. The expected times for the realization of this project are about two years.

Finally, there is a further electrification project for the mooring of the cruise ships, launched recently. This project is carried out in synergy with the first project, as the same system is used to electrify the moorings in the "Repairs Naval" area, using a submarine conductor.

7.5.7 Conclusions, closing words

Mr. Gabor Heves (REC):

With the MLW in Genoa the workshops which have involved six cities/regions of this project have been completed. This type of workshop is useful because permits to learn each with the other.

The representative of REC said that it has been very interesting because the stakeholders have debated the different aspects connected to air quality (energy, transport, health) and have discussed among them.

To think to the future, also far (2050) represents a difficult challenge and for this reason it is very important to work together and to change the behavior of the people,

At last, the representative of REC, remembered to the participants to fill the evaluation form, because it will be a useful feedback for the project.

All the results of the MLWs in the different cities will fill into a specific Report.

8 Comments

An initial appraisal of the workshops suggests that overall the workshops had a positive atmosphere and was a good experience for attendees. Participants were happy to be involved and mutually learn about and discuss air pollution, health and carbon reduction. The keynote speakers provided a good amount of information across air pollution, health, sustainable transport, climate change, and there is the opportunity to continue with the mutual learning by making the talks and posters available online. A few representatives of the MLWs will go for the Stakeholder workshops in October/November to present the view and conclusion of the MLWs.

A challenge of the workshop was supporting the groups to turn their attention to definite “actions” in the scenario session at the end. For some attendees it took time to change their focus from talking about the issues to talking about what needs, challenges, real goals in the future. The complex topics require more time for discussion on future scenarios. The facilitators had an important role on summarising and presenting the action lists to allow for a better comparison and discussion between the groups in the feedback session on the city/region in 2020, 2030 and 2050.

The feedback from the MLW participants was largely positive, highlighting in particular the opportunity to talk to people from different sectors and organisations they rarely talk to. Many participants have stated that they would like to be part of a shared workshop email contact list and follow the activities of the ClairCity project.

8.1 Initial outputs

A full analysis of the outputs on the posters from the Mutual Learning Workshop has not been carried out yet but an initial screening raises some interesting points:

2020

The poster identifies the current aims and strategies of the organisations represented by participants at the workshop. A broad range of interest were represented with many organisations already focussing on environment, health, climate change and sustainability issues. Some organisations were already involved in political groups looking at congestion, or raising awareness, or were involved in energy and air quality consultancy and planning work. Though the business sector was underrepresented at the workshops, participants from this sector identified their strategies around increasing the efficiency of their fleets and reducing waste.

2050

The participants created a poster for 2050 with vision for a “clean air”, healthy and zero-carbon city or close to zero carbon city/region related to their organisation. The posters are considered in this initial summary of the outputs, which are in the individual city/region report on the project website

Challenges and barriers

The challenges and barriers identified by participants can broadly be categorised as: political; environmental, social, business/market; housing; citizen challenges; cultural; inter-generational. .

9 Conclusions

Overall the mutual learning workshops successfully engaged with a variety of stakeholders from different sectors and organisations. As identified there was a lack of business representation at the workshops and this likely accounts for the 'gap' in in-depth discussions around business models, finance/investment, and barriers specific to business and growth.

However, though political short-termism was identified as a barrier by stakeholders, the groups' pathways from 2020 to 2050 were largely short-term (apart from one group) when it came to setting actions and milestones beyond the next five years.

This highlights the difficulties scientists, policy makers, industry and civil/civic society organisations all have in visualising potential transformative actions that go beyond the systems already in place. Future workshops could seek to address this by spending more time on pathway development and less on barriers.

The increased uptake of electric vehicles and a potential "clean air zone" in the cities are both actions/policies that have been widely discussed in national and local media recently and unsurprisingly they featured across pathways as potential policy actions.

In most of the cities clean air and air pollution are largely linked to the transport sector. The need for better transport and infrastructure planning in the cities is clearly identified and links to improved housing and better connectedness across the city. Spatial plans need to be adequately supported by effective social planning that considers health impacts, and also requires political leadership and action.

The wide representation of civil and civil society organisations led to the identification of social and cultural barriers to change, but also opportunities and potential policy actions to increase bottom-up community and citizen engagement in local governance and decision making – something the ClairCity project aims to do.

10 Stakeholder Groups

The MLW is designed for different stakeholders who are engaged in environment, health issues and policies in Bristol (reported in D 4.14), Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria region and ready to participate with their inputs in the MLW. The participants of the workshops were stakeholders, selected NGOs, social city groups, health and environmental organisations, universities, relevant department of the pilot cities, who are involved in the air quality, public health and carbon management issues, planning and activities in the city (local level), or regional and national level.

The number of the participants:

Cities:

Amsterdam: 20

Ljubljana: 16

Sosnowiec: 24

Aveiro region: 22

Liguria region: 35

In total 117 participants were present at the mutual learning workshops in Amsterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Aveiro and Liguria region.

11 Guideline: How to prepare the Mutual Learning Stakeholder Workshop

The Guideline was presented in the D4.14. It was used in the implementation of the MLW in all cities and regions. The adaptation of the Guideline to the local conditions was discussed by the city teams and the project partners in the cities and regions.

We can conclude that the MLW Guideline was very useful for preparation and facilitation of the MLW in the cities and regions.

In some cities the Guideline was translated to the local language. But most of them used the English version.